

ON PRONUNCIATION ACHIEVEMENT FACTORS AND TECHNIQUES FOR ORAL PRESENTATION

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Abstract

The article deals with the pronunciation achievement factors and techniques for oral presentation. We all know that it is difficult for adults to learn accurate pronunciation in a foreign language. We also know that some people achieve better results than others. Why is this? What are the factors that might predict which students will achieve good pronunciation? If we knew the factors helping pronunciation, we could our own learning.

Keywords. pronunciation, punctuation, knowledge, language, ability

Introduction. Richard Suter, a language researcher at a California university, decided to test the relative importance of factors that predict which students would achieve the most accurate pronunciation. He wanted to find out if there are any factors a student could change in order to improve performance. The first thing R.Suter did was to make a list of all the factors that might possibly show which would learn the best pronunciation. Then he compared these factors with the pronunciation of a group of foreign students. R.Suter presents a list of six of the factors . They are:

1. Sex.Do females learn better than males?
2. Mother tongue. Is it easier to learn a language close to ones own?
3. Personality.Do out-going people learn pronunciation better than shy people?
4. Attitude toward pronunciation. Does it make a difference if the student believes that pronunciation is a very important part of language?
5. Natural abilities. How important is the ability to mimic, or imitate? Most people assume that natural ability is the single most important factor in learning pronunciation.
6. Conversation with natives. Does the amount of conversation in English, with native speakers of English, make a significant difference?

When R.Suter compared the students pronunciation accuracy scores with these six variables, some of the results were surprising. He found that two of the factors did not have any relation to the accuracy of pronunciation. That is, these two factors were not at all significant in predicting who do well learning pronunciation. These two factors were:

1. Sex . Females were not better than males.
2. Personality.Out-doing people were not better at pronunciation than shy people.

R.Suter concluded from these results that the factors of sex and personality were not significant predictors of pronunciation accuracy. On the other hand, he found that four variables did make a significant difference. I will give them to you in order of importance. That is,the most important predictors come first.

1. Mother tongue. This was the most significant factor in predicting achievement. If the students own

language was closer to English, the achievement was likely to be greater.

2. Attitude about pronunciation. This was the second most important factor in predicting achievement. In fact, a belief in the importance of pronunciation was far more important than any of the remaining factors. After the mother tongue factor, this factor of attitude was the single most significant variable in predicting good pronunciation learning.

3. Conversation with natives. The third most important variable was the amount of time the student spent in conversation with native speakers of English.

4. Natural ability. This was the least important variable. The ability to imitate helped, but it was not nearly as significant as most people think. It was far less significant than the first three.

R.Suter concluded that the three most significant predictors in achievement in pronunciation are:1.the students mother tongue,2.the belief in the importance of pronunciation,2.the amount of time spent in conversations with native speakers.

The conclusions of this research are encouraging. Of course, we cant change factor1, the mother tongue. But we do have control over factors 2 and 3, which are the next most important variables in learning accurate pronunciation. First, we can decide that pronunciation is important, and second, we can choose to make the effort to speak the new language with natives. You might say that our own choice is the most significant factor in achievement in the new language.

Today I want to tell you about some useful research on the way English speakers help their listeners. You know that a lot of English sentences are very complicated. The listener can get confused if the thought groups aren't clearly divided. If the groups are not clear, the ideas will not be clear. Each language has special ways to mark thought groups, but in English the chief marker is intonation. A researcher named O' Malley thought of a clever way to study these markers. He knew that algebra problems have to be written with parentheses. These punctuation markers are used to group the terms. If the algebra is spoken out loud, a native speaker of English can hear the grouping. Let me give you an example. Write down this equation:

$$A+(BC) =Y$$

Now write down another one:

$$(A+B) C = Y$$

Did you write them differently? You should have put the parentheses in different places, because these equations are different.

Perhaps you can get the idea better if I use examples from arithmetic. Write down this problem:

$$2+(3 \times 4)=14$$

Now write :

$$(2+3) \times 4=20$$

Did you put the parentheses in different places? The terms are exactly the same, but the grouping is different. That is why the answers are different.

The same concept of grouping also applies to words. Here's an example:

"John," said the boss, "is stupid."

That has a very different meaning from this sentence, using the same words/

John said, "the boss is stupid."

The meaning is different, just as in algebra or arithmetic. So grouping is important. Of course, speaking isn't like writing. We don't use parentheses or other punctuation when we are speaking. In fact, punctuation was invented to try to show some of the things we do in speech to separate groups of words. Written language substitutes punctuation for the spoken signals of intonation. The English listener depends on this intonation signals in order to understand clearly.

In his research on the subject of thought-group markers, O'Malley tape recorded native English speakers reading algebraic equations aloud. Then he asked some other English speakers to listen to the recordings and decided where the parentheses were placed. O'Malley found that both the speakers and the listeners were very consistent in grouping the terms. The listeners were able to identify the placement of the parentheses because the speakers used two markers to show the end of a group.

The first marker was silence. That is, the speaker paused after the group, to make clear that it was finished. Listen for the pause when I read this equation:

$$A \dots + (B \times C) \dots = Y$$

Marker 1, a pause, is quite powerful in slow speech. But in more rapid speech, there isn't time for many pauses. So the speaker has to rely on another method to mark the end of group. Marker 2 is a change of pitch. Usually the voice pitch drops low at the end of a group. Generally a high pitch means a new idea, end a low pitch means the end of an idea. Listen for the pitch change when I read this equation.

$$(A+B) \times C = Y$$

Other researches have confirmed this findings for spoken English. In both algebraic formulas spoken English, the thought groups are divided by the same two markers. With Marker 1, which is especially used for slow speech, the speaker pauses at the end of each group. With Marker 2, the voice falls at the end of a group. For special clarity, both markers are used.

I have reviewed some of this researches because it shows a very important way to help our listeners understand us easily. It demonstrates the ways of making thought groups clear. Clear thought groups are part of clear speech.

In your university work, you will be expected to give oral presentations, in the form of reports or simply in the form of answers to questions. There are several things you can do to make your oral presentations clear and easy to understand.

The essential point to realize is that speech and writing are different. If you want to be clearly understood, you can't simply read your written report aloud. The biggest difference between spoken and written language is that readers can look back over the printed words when they don't understand. In spoken language, however, listeners can't go back and check the words. They can rely only on memory. So the first principle to keep in mind when you are planning to speak in public is that you have to help the listener's memory. This means that an oral report can't deliver information as rapidly as a written report. That is, you can't have as many pieces of new information packed into the same number of words, because they will come at too fast a rate for the listeners to understand.

In an oral report, the rate of delivery has to be slower. One of the best ways to help your audience is simply to speak slowly. Many people speak too fast when they speak to a group. This is a mistake, especially if you have a foreign accent, because it makes listening more difficult. Beyond the simple technique of speaking more slowly when you speak before a group, there are ways of organizing your presentation that can help the listener recognize and understand your main points.

The organization of your talk should allow enough time for the listener to think both before and after each new idea. The purpose of the time before the new information is to give the audience a chance to understand the background clearly. Knowledge of the background, or setting of the information, makes it much easier to anticipate what kind of information is coming next. If the new information occurs too early, without enough background, the listener isn't prepared to understand the new idea. So before each piece of information, the listeners should be prepared with enough background to be able to predict what's coming.

I've been describing the time for thinking before the new information. It's also important to provide time for thinking after the new information. This thinking time allows listeners to fit the idea into their general knowledge of the subject. Thinking time gives the listener a chance to make sure the idea was understood before going on to the next new idea.

There are three common ways to give the listener time for thinking after a point of new information. One way is simply to pause. A moment of silence gives the listener time to take in the new information. But there are other ways. A second method is to use a paraphrase. That is, you say the same thing, but in different words. This paraphrase, or repetition of the idea, helps the listeners to fix the thought in their memory. A third way to give the listener time to think is to use words that don't mean much. These are words that convey no information, but just fill time. For instance, you might say something like "as I've been saying" or "and so forth and so on." That kind of expression doesn't really say anything. It's just made of what we call "filler words."

The words have no real meaning, but they do perform a useful function, since they allow the listener time to think.

Conclusion

In summary, then, we know that oral language should deliver information at a slower rate than you can use in written language. New information should be presented more gradually. Thinking time should be provided both before and after each important new item. The time before is to provide a background so that the listeners can have a chance to anticipate the idea. The time after is to allow the listeners a chance to understand what they just heard. The three most common ways to allow this thinking time are: (1) to pause, (2) to paraphrase, and (3) to use filler words.

I hope that these suggestions will help make your oral presentation a great success.

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